

DRIVING FORWARD INCLUSIVE GENDER ANALYSIS IN R&I POLICIES

Recommendations for Framework Programme 10

The gender dimension in R&I has been one of the EU's objectives for achieving gender equality in R&I since 2012. Successive Framework Programmes have had a clear impact on national RFOs in terms of gender equality measures. The introduction in Horizon 2020 of flagged topics in which a sex/gender analysis should be explored and the requirement to include a sex/gender analysis by default as an award criterion in Horizon Europe were two outstanding steps on this journey. However, the field of policies on Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I content in the ERA needs to be further strengthened in terms of visibility, financial support, and training in order to achieve its objective.

Two major challenges today refer to the monitoring and evaluation of these policies and the difficulties of making intersectionality operational at the RFO level. This adds to the traditional confusion between gender balance and sex/gender analysis that still exists in some organisations. Moreover, resistant arguments that emerged from different sectors of the R&I field point to the complexity of the field and the lack of understanding in R&I communities to call for further simplification of these policies. To reflect on the progress and challenges of integrating an Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I, a stakeholder consultation workshop was organised by GENDERACTIONplus that included experienced RFOs from the ERA, Canada, and the United States. Some of the GENDERACTIONplus recommendations for the upcoming Framework Programme 10 that resulted from these discussions and can be found in this position paper include:

- Make gender analysis in the content of R&I visible again
- Coordinate and align policy on agendas in the ERA using a whole sector approach
- Strengthen the evaluation procedure for the upcoming FP10
- Use financial instruments to produce new knowledge and methods
- Give the NCP system a boost

Introduction

Integrating a gender dimension into content research and innovation (R&I) contributes to enhancing scientific rigour, uncovering hidden biases, and producing more accurate, comprehensive, and applicable research outcomes (Schiebinger et al., 2011)¹ with societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology, and innovation (European Commission, 2020). Nevertheless, people's experiences of discrimination are multi-dimensional and complex, shaped by different factors and social dynamics operating together (Hankivsky, 2014).² Therefore, including diverse perspectives in R&I shapes the processes and outcomes of knowledge production and teaching within them, which in turn influences how societal problems are addressed and which inequalities are considered in societal change processes (Eigenmann et al., 2024).³ For this reason, opening our perspective towards an Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I has been one of the most important debates among leading institutions in recent years.

An Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I Content refers to the consideration of diverse factors of inequality that may intersect with sex/gender in a given object of study as well as to the need to include diverse target groups and end-users in research and innovation projects.

ERA Forum Subgroup on Inclusive Gender Equality (2024)

The GENDERACTIONplus project has been promoting advice that brings these policies into the current debates and pushes them forward. Key R&I agents in the implementation of these policies are research funding organisations (RFOs) and several actions were planned to support them. On the one hand, the need to support those institutions with less experience, mainly from widening countries, has been covered through engagement with the GENDERACTIONplus RFO Community of Practice (CoP) and the development

1 | Schiebinger, L., Klinge, I., Sánchez de Madariaga, I., Paik, H. Y., Schraudner, M., and Stefanick, M. (Eds.) (2011-2024). *Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering and Environment*.

2 | Olena Hankivsky (2014). *Intersectionality 101*. Institute for Intersectionality Research and Policy, Simon Fraser University.

3 | Laura Eigenmann et al. (2024). *Intersectional transformation or 'gender equality+'? Intersectionality in European Union policies on research and science*. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*. 10.1332/25151088Y2024D000000053.

of online training on the gender dimension in R&I.⁴ On the other hand, the need to seek new ideas for the future and learn from the most experienced institutions led to the organisation of a stakeholder consultation workshop on Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I with a key group of funding agencies. Acknowledging the role referents played in the promotion of these policies,⁵ two institutions from Canada and the US that fund health research participated in the stakeholder consultation workshop to engage in discussions with funding agencies of the European Research Area (ERA).

This position paper is based on the discussions and ideas exchanged during an online stakeholder consultation workshop titled 'Inclusive Gender Analysis in Research and Innovation: Beyond the European Research Area', held on 1 October 2024.⁶ Both the challenges expressed by the participants⁷ and the promising practices observed have helped GENDERACTIONplus to make previous ideas on how to make Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I by RFOs more complex and grounded in the reality of funding agencies. Successive Framework Programmes for R&I developed by the European Commission (EC) have been a clear trendsetter for RFOs when it comes to the gender dimension in R&I,⁸ and with this position paper GENDERACTIONplus aims to provide recommendations on how Framework Programme 10 (FP10) can continue to maintain this role.

Progress and monitoring: Higher policy uptake through awareness raising

Progress is reported in terms of the monitoring and evaluation of integrating a sex/gender analysis in R&I projects. The monitoring process starts from the moment a topic is formulated and is part of all the stages of project evaluation and of the funding cycle.⁹ In the case of the EC, the shift conducted in its policy towards a default requirement to consider sex/gender analysis in R&I projects has led to only 5% of funded projects being exempted from this mandatory requirement.¹⁰ Indeed, there has been an increase in the number of Horizon Europe topics that address sex/gender aspects from Work

4 | <https://genderaction.eu/introducing-the-online-course-on-gender-dimension-in-research-and-innovation-for-national-contact-points/>

5 | See Barr, Elizabeth et al. (2023). Reflecting on Progress in and Establishing Benchmarks for Sex and Gender Health Education. Available at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37734039/>

6 | <https://genderaction.eu/events/eu-genderactionplus-hosts-stakeholder-consultation-on-inclusive-gender-analysis-in-research-and-innovation/>

7 | Participants: Gender Sector of the DG-RTD at the EC, Vinnova, CIHR, US National Institutes of Health, AEI, SFI, ANR, NSERC, Kilden, Joanneum, FRRB. Organised by: BNSF, FECYT, TACR, facilitated by VA, as part of the GENDERACTIONplus WP4 Gender Dimension in R&I.

8 | Trine Rogg, K., Lydia, G., & Jana, D. (2023). GENDERACTIONplus D4.1: Benchmarking and assessment report on guidelines for sex/gender analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12795890>

9 | Infographics by the Task Force to be available in 2025.

10 | Data provided by the European Commission during the GENDERACTIONplus Workshop on Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I Content beyond the ERA (1 October 2024).

Programmes 2021-2022 to 2023-2024, according to the monitoring at FP level conducted by the Gender Sector of the DG RTD.¹¹

Thanks to the monitoring of the measures to promote sex/gender analysis adopted by RFOs, experts from the Gender Sector of the DG RTD, VINNOVA, and the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), report that the share of applicants integrating a sex/gender analysis in research topics and as an aspect of their work is rising. In this sense, it can be argued that requiring applicants to explain how they are integrating a sex/gender analysis has had an impact in quantitative terms. For instance, the CIHR¹² reported great progress in the proportion of research investments that address sex and/or gender considerations from 33.9% in 2014 to 86.4% in 2024. The efforts that led to this improvement are related to online training modules for applicants, the completion of which was part of the application, to the training of peer reviewers, and to the provision of methods and measures guidance to the research community that could help them methodologically and enable them to address intellectual challenges. It should be noted that since 2021 the method the CIHR uses to assess this question differentiates between the sex and gender aspects of health research and has revealed that while the integration of sex in their funded research has increased to up to 90% of projects in a decade, gender aspects are still harder to consider by health researchers.¹³

However, **qualitative insights are less commonly collected** by funding agencies. Collecting information from funded research and innovation on the added value of integrating an inclusive gender analysis in their projects and how doing so improved their content has ample room for improvement. RFOs like VINNOVA¹⁴ and the CIHR are currently exploring ways of categorising and analysing the responses and motivations to their question on sex/gender analysis in project application templates in order to help researchers understand these topics and increase their ability to apply gender lenses to their research and innovation solutions. This is an ambitious task even for the most experienced funders and one in which mutual learning and sharing of experiences is required.

An integral part of the monitoring process, as stated by experts from the CIHR, is to generate the evidence necessary for the R&I community and to persuade them that integrating sex/gender aspects – where relevant – in R&I content improves the quality of science and innovation. **'It is about showing impact'**, as the CIHR stated during the stakeholder consultation. The success of policies depends to a large extent on the degree of **awareness among the research and innovation communities** that sex/gender analysis leads to better science. Mandatory training for leading researchers has been one of the strategies followed by the CIHR to promote an increase in the number of health projects that consider sex and gender. VINNOVA have begun assessing the ways in which researchers and innovators have found the integration of an inclusive gender analysis useful, and indicators ranging from an increased understanding of the research problem to the identification of new markets may well be useful signs of the community's awareness.

¹¹ | Information provided by the EC representative during the Stakeholder Consultation Workshop.

¹² | <https://cihr-irsc.gc.ca/e/193.html>

¹³ | CIHR (2023). A New Era of Sex and Gender Science. Impact Report 2015–2022. https://cihr-irsc.gc.ca/e/documents/igh_report_new_era_sgc-en.pdf

¹⁴ | Vinnova, Sweden's innovation agency, <https://www.vinnova.se/en/>

The difficulties of making intersectionality operational

In spite of the increasing attention to the intersectional approach in R&I policies in recent years both in the North American and European contexts, it is difficult to find examples of research funders that are making intersectionality and inclusiveness operational. This occurs in a more general context where EU gender equality policies in R&I remain focused mainly on gender, and other categories are mentioned but rarely deeply explored (Eigenmann et al., 2024).¹⁵ For the CIHR, intersectionality is seen as ‘a direction forward’ by moving from their traditional concept of ‘sex and gender-based analysis’ (SGBA) to SGBA+ as a way to systematically include other diversity dimensions. The difficulties in some countries like France to collect and cross data based on gender, race, and religion were also pointed out by the French National Research Agency (ANR).¹⁶ Moreover, some RFOs stress that before incorporating intersectionality, it is crucial to first assess the capacity of the applicants to employ such a challenging perspective. This is the reason why there are few research funders that include inclusiveness aspects in the question requiring applicants to incorporate a sex/gender analysis in their research proposals. According to VINNOVA’s experience, ‘the question does not contain the word intersectionality or inclusion yet because we see that we have to set the capacity for our applicants to first be able to have high-quality motivations’. Regardless, most academic applicants in Sweden engaging with VINNOVA have tended to integrate an intersectional perspective, even if it is not explicitly required, since sex, gender, and intersectional perspectives have been part of higher education curricula in most scientific fields in recent decades.

As pointed out by several experts participating in the stakeholder consultation workshop, including other variables in the question for applicants, while important, is not the only way to promote intersectional perspectives. Offering training and resources as well as providing constructive feedback to applicants as a way to enhance their performance on these aspects were highlighted as key measures. At VINNOVA, for instance, an innovative design method is employed that encourages the design of innovation proposals from a norm-critical perspective by asking who benefits from the innovation, and thus actively challenging the norms that perpetuate exclusion and discrimination. This approach evolves into a norm-creative process, fostering collective, inclusive, and co-creative solutions.

When it comes to other actors, the business enterprise sector (BES) shows specific difficulties understanding and integrating an inclusiveness perspective. This is due to the fact that private companies may have different roles and perspectives in the field of gender equality policies. Observations from both VINNOVA and Joanneum Research¹⁷ highlight

15 | Laura Eigenmann et al (2024). Intersectional transformation or ‘gender equality+’? Intersectionality in European Union policies on research and science. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*. <https://doi.org/10.1332/25151088Y2024D000000053>

16 | Agence Nationale de la Recherche <https://anr.fr/>

17 | Non-university research company, <https://www.joanneum.at/en/>

that industry applicants often are not familiar with specific gender equality terms and require more knowledge on how to differentiate between gender balance in project teams and sex/gender analysis in R&I content. However, some do focus on diverse customer needs when following a human-centred design approach without naming this a gender or intersectional approach (Schiffbänker & Walker, forthcoming 2025).¹⁸

Therefore, the experts agreed that a **solid foundation of knowledge in sex and gender analysis is essential** for progressing towards intersectionality.¹⁹ This is particularly relevant in a context in which resistant discourses point to the intersectional approach as an additional burden. To counter this argument and stress the added value of this new perspective, showcasing successful examples, role model institutions, and promising practices is vital. It is also important to be responsive to pushbacks, by providing applicants and reviewers with resources and guidance to navigate methodological, data, and analytical challenges.

Training plays a key role in building capacity; incentives such as funding opportunities that focus on intersectional methods and measures can serve as powerful motivators for promoting change. Political support is crucial and is most effective when coupled with binding regulations and clearly defined administrative rules. Encouraging researchers and innovators to emphasise a gender analysis with an intersectional perspective in their research topics and innovation solutions is essential. Reviewers are pivotal to the integration of these aspects in research and innovation since they play a significant role in evaluating projects. Therefore, trainings and clear instructions on how to assess the applicability and impact of inclusiveness aspects in project proposals is vital. Explaining the underlying arguments and presenting good practice examples from various scientific fields might help reviewers to develop awareness and creativity on how to assess gender in R&I as would producing support material provided by RFOs that contains guiding questions or illustrative examples (Schiffbänker, 2024).²⁰ This will help redefine standards for research excellence and will foster a more equitable and comprehensive approach to scientific inquiry, ensuring that diverse perspectives are meaningfully incorporated into the research process and its outcomes. This is a process that takes time and requires effort at all levels.

18 | Schiffbänker, H., Walker, D. (2025 forthcoming): Policies to integrate gender in innovation, Case study2: FEMtech reseach projects, <https://www.inspirequality.eu/>

19 | This idea was also stressed in Trine Rogg, K., Lydia, G., & Jana, D. (2023). GENDERACTIONplus D4.1: Benchmarking and assessment report on guidelines for sex/gender analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12795890>

20 | Schiffbänker, H., Sauer, A., & Peterson, H. (2024). GRANteD D6.3 Reforming peer review practices – lessons learned from the implementation of gender equality policies in Research Funding Organisations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14044093>

The current main challenges from the perspective of funding agencies

Different contexts and support

This diversity is partly due to the different global regions invited to participate in the discussion in the RFO stakeholder consultation workshop, including Canada and the US. However, within the ERA there are also diverse contexts and speeds in the advancement of these specific policies as mapped by the GENDERACTIONplus project.²¹ The political moment may certainly act as an enabler for the advancement in these policies at the RFO level or as a ‘loudspeaker’ for the resistant discourse. No one-size-fits-all solution for every funding agency in every context was identified, but rather a common willingness to drive forward these policies as a matter of research quality and societal relevance: ‘Taking the sex and/or gender dimension into account in the research content is a matter of social responsibility of science and of a rigorous scientific approach’, according to the ANR as stated during the stakeholder consultation workshop. The diversity of cultural and political contexts is the reason why the alignment of agendas in the framework of the ERA Policy Agenda 2025–2027 and mutual learning among funding agencies, such as the one conducted in the GENDERACTIONplus RFO CoP, are key to having all funding agencies and national authorities on board.

Understanding issues

The rapid evolution of terminology presents challenges for understanding basic concepts in the field by newcomers. This issue was also observed by the ANR in a pilot from a 2021 call for proposals where candidates were asked to explain how they took the sex and/or gender dimension into consideration in their project for internal, analytical purposes. This includes the BES, that faces the challenge of aligning funding terminology with concepts and approaches used in the business enterprise sector. This may lead to some reluctance to update language in line with the dynamic changes in gender studies. For instance, moving from a binary conceptualisation of sex, gender, and sexual orientation to a non-binary approach in the content of research was highlighted as a challenge, even if there are examples of this being done, such as by the US National Institutes of Health (NIH), which have stressed the recognition of diverse gender identities and sexual orientations in their internal documents by mentioning LGBTIQ+ people. In this sense, specific support for key sectors such as industry to build the necessary capacities – and to link them to the approaches they apply – should be an imperative task for the upcoming FP10. Indeed, there are still difficulties in terms of understanding and integrating what a sex/gender analysis in R&I means, and even more so in terms of what it means to integrate an intersectional perspective. From a policy perspective, the GENDERACTIONplus

21 | Trine Rogg, K., Lydia, G., & Jana, D. (2023). GENDERACTIONplus D4.1: Benchmarking and assessment report on guidelines for sex/gender analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12795890>

benchmark already suggested the risk of building upon a weak foundation in basic gender issues and the risk of inclusiveness-related concepts being misused.²²

Intellectual challenges

Integrating sex/gender aspects among research topics as well as intersectionality raises analytical and methodological difficulties. This involves adopting new methods and techniques for ensuring that the research accurately captures the complexities of diverse identities, experiences, and inequalities. Obstacles in obtaining data on other categories than sex-disaggregated data are also part of these discussions.²³ Even internally at agencies funding health research, there are difficulties understanding the complexity of sex and its multiple aspects. To facilitate the adoption of an inclusive gender analysis in R&I content, it is crucial to provide clear, practical guidelines. These should outline how to design studies that effectively integrate intersectional perspectives, including recommendations on sample sizing, data collection, and analytical strategies. By equipping researchers, reviewers, and innovators with the necessary tools and frameworks, the transition to more inclusive and intersectionality-aware research practices can be made more manageable.

Emerging resistances that consider an Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I an additional burden

Resistances to gender equality have been widely explored by the gender & science community in the ERA for years. Yet the field of inclusive gender analysis in R&I faces its own resistance, since gender lenses reveal the biases and limited research results and innovation solutions from gender-blind R&I. In this way, critiques posed from a gender perspective challenge both the claimed objectivity of science and the way we do science. For instance, in the context of Sweden, which has a long tradition of a government mandate targeting RFOs to incorporate gender analysis in the research funded, policies to promote a sex/gender analysis were described at the time as a threat to academic freedom and independent thinking that was backed by 'political interests' (Johanson, 2024).²⁴ The ANR has detected some resistance from the research community in relation to the policy of sex/gender analysis in RFOs based on the idea that such analysis is irrelevant for certain areas of knowledge, while the NIH has encountered some backlash as a result of their courses on sex/gender in health research policy. Currently, one of the arguments levelled against funding agencies is that sex/gender analysis in R&I, and particularly the inclusiveness aspects, constitutes an additional burden in application forms

22 | Trine Rogg, K., Lydia, G., & Jana, D. (2023). GENDERACTIONplus D4.1: Benchmarking and assessment report on guidelines for sex/gender analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12795890>

23 | See Christopher Cederroth et al. (2024). Integrating gender analysis into research: reflections from the Gender-Net Plus workshop. *The Lancet*. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/eclinm/article/PIIS2589-5370\(24\)00307-9/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/eclinm/article/PIIS2589-5370(24)00307-9/fulltext)

24 | Evelina Johanson (2024). Sex and Gender Perspectives as Quality? On the Controversy About Gender and Science in the Swedish Research Debate. *NORA – Nordic Journal of Feminist and Gender Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08038740.2023.2299460>

and in the evaluation process, according to several experts. This resonates with the current discourse at the EU level that is calling for the simplification of applications and procedures, and has particularly targeted issues of Responsible Research and Innovation, such as gender equality and sex/gender analysis from an intersectional perspective.²⁵ This leaves RFOs no choice but to take a firm stance and actively promote an Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I policy with decisive support from the hierarchy of institutions. As one expert stated, **'we need to promote the policy instead of arguing that it is too early to require intersectionality'**.

Recommendations for the upcoming FP10 as a trendsetter

This position paper reflects some of the current debates and pressing obstacles that funding agencies are confronted with in relation to the efforts to advance the use of an Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I. The policies on inclusive gender analysis in R&I content in the ERA needs to be further strengthened in terms of visibility, financial support, and training in order to achieve its objective. Therefore, several recommendations should be considered for the upcoming Framework Programme as a trendsetter for RFOs of the ERA:

Analysing existing gaps and challenges at the FP level to fully integrate gender and intersectional analysis in R&I, including instruments for better monitoring implementation, results, and impact. The Gender Sector of the DG RTD is currently planning a study in 2025 to help understand how the sex/gender analysis is addressed in R&I projects that are ongoing. Clear standards for successful gender-inclusive projects as well as intersectionality-sensitive research methodologies could help provide researchers and innovators with guidance in the process. Instruments like interactive dashboards that display progress with indicators across different parts of the FP could help make the process more transparent and contribute to robust progress.

- Potential quantitative indicators and qualitative insights at the FP level should consider at least the work programmes, the evaluation process, funded projects, and scientific publications, namely:
 - No. of Horizon Europe topics that refer explicitly to sex/gender analysis, including intersectional aspects when applicable
 - Percentage of the reviewers who have received training on sex/gender analysis and intersectionality provided by the EC
 - No. of panels that include at least one gender expert
 - Percentage of project proposals that refer to sex/gender and intersectional factors in their research objectives and/or abstracts
 - No. of scientific publications resulting from projects funded by Horizon Europe that highlight an inclusive gender analysis in R&I based on keywords
 - Case studies/success stories showcasing the integration of an inclusive gender analysis in R&I content, especially in STEM fields and innovation actions

25 | See ERAC Opinion on Guidance for the next Framework Programme for Research & Innovation (2024), p.15. Available at <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-11678-2024-INIT/en/pdf>

Making gender analysis in the content of R&I visible again:

- Design a communication strategy that can translate the EC framework for sex/gender analysis and intersectionality as stated in Gendered Innovations 2²⁶ into a political commitment that should be transmitted to all relevant actors: DG RTD, ERAC, ERA Forum, reviewers for FP10, RFOs, umbrella organisations, relevant scientific societies and journals at the EU level, and COARA promoters, among others. Communication campaigns with key messages explaining and supporting an inclusive gender analysis in R&I should energise the policy content and the political commitment, thus acting as a decisive trendsetter.
- Elaborate methodological guidance and support that would help researchers and innovators overcome scientific challenges by nurturing reports such as Gendered Innovations 2 with new examples of research.
- Present good examples and promising practices from projects funded by Horizon Europe showcasing that integrating an inclusive gender analysis makes research and innovation better.
- Build capacity via trainings and workshops tailored for scientists, peer reviewers, and BES and industry actors – for instance, by developing further the online course on the gender dimension in R&I for NCPs²⁷ or supporting peer2peer learning, especially for the BES sector (Schiffbänker et al., 2024).²⁸
- Collate data sources to support evidence-based decision-making in a robust database to systematically collect, manage, and analyse data on gender and inclusiveness in R&I.

What to do when faced with the complexity of a research topic: does simplification ensure scientific rigour, or should curiosity, creativity, and intellectual challenge guide us?

Strengthening the evaluation procedure for the upcoming FP10:

- Continuous monitoring and feedback throughout the project lifecycle.
- Elaborate a set of indicators that would keep track not only of direct results but also of impact.

26 | <https://op.europa.eu/es/publication-detail/-/publication/33b4c99f-2e66-11eb-b27b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

27 | <https://genderaction.eu/introducing-the-online-course-on-gender-dimension-in-research-and-innovation-for-national-contact-points/>

28 | Schiffbänker, H., Sauer, A., & Peterson, H. (2024). GRANteD D6.3 Reforming peer review practices – lessons learned from the implementation of gender equality policies in Research Funding Organisations

- Guarantee gender expertise among reviewers and evaluation panels at all levels of the Framework Programme ensuring an adequate budget for this endeavour. Research has shown that when evaluation panels have gender expertise, the sex/gender analysis is likely to be considered (Hunt et al., 2022).²⁹

Policy coordination and alignment of agendas in the ERA from a whole sector approach: New indicators and principles to integrate and evaluate an inclusive gender analysis in R&I content in cooperation with national RFOs are foreseen in the ERA Action 5 *Gender Equality and Inclusiveness* (ERA Policy Agenda, 2022–2024).³⁰

- Support at the highest policy level of the EC and national authorities with competences in R&I are needed in order to advance the upcoming ERA Policy Agenda 2025–2027 in the field of inclusive gender analysis in R&I from a whole sector approach that involves all relevant actors and stakeholders.³¹

Financial instruments to produce new knowledge and methods: It is crucial to have updated and more diverse examples in order to prompt researchers and innovators to adopt an inclusive gender analysis in their project. Instruments that FP10 could adopt include:

- **Co-funding programmes** in cooperation with RFOs that enable interdisciplinary and international collaborations in knowledge generation on gender studies and intersectionality, thus contributing to the alignment of agendas in the ERA.³²
- **European Innovation Council quality indicators** require an inclusive gender analysis perspective in the development of innovation solutions.
- **Prize for the best research publication** integrating an inclusive gender analysis in the framework of a Horizon Europe funded project, with special emphasis on early-career researchers.

Give the NCP system a boost: Ensure that national NCP structures nominate gender NCPs who should be visible on the NCP websites and coordinated in a European network of gender NCPs ready to support these policies in view of the upcoming FP10. The mandate for all NCPs should be expanded to include the promotion of an inclusive gender analysis across the whole FP in addition to the promotion of gender balance and equal opportunities.

These recommendations are aligned with – and designed to complement – the ideas expressed by the ERA Action 5 Subgroup in its Framework for the Integration and Evaluation of an Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I³³ as well as the position paper on FP10

²⁹ | Hunt, Lilian, Mathias Nielsen, and Londa Schiebinger. (2022). A framework for sex, gender, and diversity analysis in research: *Science* vol. 377, no. 6614: 1492-1495. DOI: 10.1126/science.abp9775.

³⁰ | https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf

³¹ | Witt, Alice, Marina Politis, and Kate Womersley. (2023). A whole sector approach to policy change will accelerate integration of sex and gender in research: *BMJ* 2023; 383. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.p2913>

³² | See the previous experience of the ERA-NET Cofund GENDER-Net Plus <https://gender-net-plus.eu/>

³³ | To be available in 2025.

released by this Subgroup.³⁴ Different committed stakeholders, among which we count the upcoming FP10, are **united in the powerful idea – the only one that can confront resistant discourse – that more accurate knowledge is not only good in itself for the quality of research and innovation, but it also leads to a more just society** (Johanson, 2024).³⁵ The above recommendations constitute practical ways of making this powerful idea a reality for the ERA.

The upcoming FP10 has the capacity to provide an enormous boost to the process of incorporating an inclusive gender analysis in R&I in contemporary scientific quality standards and to create the tools for better understanding, accepting, and endorsing the idea that an Inclusive Gender Analysis in R&I leads to better science and solutions and, ultimately, to more equal societies.

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34 | [Link to the document if available before publication](#)

35 | Evelina Johanson (2024). Sex and Gender Perspectives as Quality? On the Controversy About Gender and Science in the Swedish Research Debate. NORA – Nordic Journal of Feminist and Gender Research.

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